

Maritime Trade and rise of towns on the Coromandel Coast under the English: 1690-1799 -With Special reference to Cuddalore

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ABSTRACT

The towns like Madras, Pondicherry, For St. David, Cuddalore, Porto novo, Tranqubar and Nagapattinam grew around fort and port. The people who migrated to towns from the rural areas in search of employment, market for their produce, education and medical facilities added to the existing non-agricultural population. Cuddalore under the English emerged into a military town in the eighteenth century. It may be made to the Portuguese settlements in Santhome, Cuddalore, Porto Novo and Nagapattinam established between the middle of the sixteenth century and early part of the seventeenth century. The Dutch created settlements in Petapoli, Pulicat and Cuddalore in the early part of the seventeenth century and in Porto Novo and Nagapattinam in the last quarter of the seventeenth century.

All these coastal towns grew around the fort and the port with an exception to the Dutch settlement in the island of Pulicat in Chengalpattu district where there was no port. Though the urban area was distinct from the rural area in physical appearance due to the infrastructural facilities available in the former, the attitude of a section of the urban dwellers was still rural. Urbanization does not mean mere increase of concrete buildings of secular and religious nature. Likewise, mere increase of population alone cannot be criteria for assessing urban growth.

Key Words: Maritime Trade, Population, Urbanization, Cuddalore, Settlements

Introduction

Colonial towns came into existence to facilitate maritime trade of the Europeans on the Coromandel spanning from Cape Comorin in the South to the Mahanadi in the north during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. The towns like Madras, Pondicherry, Fort St. David, Cuddalore, Porto novo, Tranqubar and Nagapattinam grew around fort and port. Maritime trade, missionary activities, spread of western education and administration of the English East India Company brought about change of occupation, economy, society, food habits and life-style of the natives. The people who migrated to towns from the rural areas in search of employment, market for their produce, education and medical facilities added to the existing non-agricultural population. Cuddalore under the English emerged into a military town in the eighteenth century.

Trading settlements

The European traders who were busy in spice trade in the west coast were attracted by the finest variety of cotton fabrics produced in the Coromandel coastal region. As there was a demand for these cloths in South-east Asia and Europe, Trading Companies of various European countries such as Portugal, Holland, France and England established trading settlements in the different places on the Coromandel coast. Mention may be made to the Portuguese settlements in Santhome, Cuddalore, Porto Novo and Nagapattinam established between the middle of the sixteenth century and early part of the seventeenth century. The Dutch created settlements in Petapoli, Pulicat and Cuddalore in the early part of the seventeenth century and in Porto Novo and Nagapattinam in the last quarter of the seventeenth century. English erected Fort St. George in Madras in 1639. They ousted the Dutch, their immediate rivals from Cuddalore in 1690 and Nagapattinam in 1784 and acquired monopoly of maritime trade. All these coastal towns grew around the fort and the port with an exception to the Dutch settlement in the island of Pulicat in Chengalpattu district where there was no port.

Creation of settlements and emergence of Cantonments in Cuddalore

The Cowle granted by the Subedar major on behalf of the ruler of the Senji country in 1681 guaranteed the English to conduct free and uninterrupted trade in Cuddalore. The first

factory building was erected by the English at Cuddalore in 1683. After the purchase of the coastal village of Devanampattinam along with a castle belonged to an indigenous merchant called Chinniah chetty from Ramaraja, the ruler of Senji country in 1690, the English named the place Fort St. David.¹ Since then Cuddalore and Devanampattinam were collectively called Fort St. David due to the proximity of these two places by sea. On the expansion of Cuddalore by random shot from Fort St. David, the Dutch who conducted cloth trade from Manjakuppam village were evicted from there ignoring the instruction of the ruler of Senji in 1693.

Emergence of military towns in Devanampattinam and Cuddalore

The place of greatest historical interest at Cuddalore is Fort. St. David. The ruins of which still exists. The castle close to the northern branch of the river Gadilam was modified and used as Agency House as well as the residence of the Deputy Governor of Fort. St. David. By the middle of the eighteenth century the course of the river Gadilam was changed on the western side of the fort by digging a canal which connected Gadilam river with Pennayar river in the north. Devanampattinam was fortified along with bastion, bomb proof barracks, battery and obsolete redoubts fitted with guns by the middle of the eighteenth century. The Dutch factory house called Tevanampatam was demolished.²

By the middle of the eighteenth century the garrison in Fort. St. David consisted of “1,600 natives- sepoys, lascars and topasses; 619 Europeans, of whom 286 were effective; 83 pensioners or infirm; and 250 seamen, the crews of the Triton and Bridgwater, which had run ashore on the appearance of the French squadron.”³ The purpose of converting Devanampattinam into a military base was to safeguard the English from the enemies, especially the French and to conduct safe trade. Fort St. David was the headquarters of the English possessions on the Coromandel coast from 1746 to 1752.

By this time Cuddalore (Present Port town) also was converted into a cantonment with fortification on all three sides. A powder magazine was built in the island lying in between Devanampattinam and Cuddalore. Buildings at Padirikuppam near Tiruppapuliur were built for the troop of European cavalry. “The fortifications of Cuddalore were all demolished in 1803 and the only building in it (besides Christ Church) which still survives to bear testimony to former

importance is the Old Factory House, now used as godown by Messrs. Parry & Company. There had apparently been some sort of a Factory House at Cuddalore Old Town from the earliest years of the settlement there and in 1707 the Company bought the House of Mr. Haynes partly as a residence for the Deputy Governor of Fort. St. David when he went to stay in Old Town and partly to serve as a 'Citadel' for the fort there. When the French took Cuddalore and Fort St. David in 1758 they destroyed what remained of the building." The Anglo-French war continued till 1785 when Cuddalore was restored to the English and Pondicherry to the French by means of peace treaty.⁴

Textile trade

The finest variety of cotton cloths woven in and around Cuddlore and connection of rivers Gadilam and Pennayar with sea induced the French and English Trading Companies to have control over Cuddalore. The final success of the English in creating settlements and fortifying them made the English masters of the land and helped free trade. Textile trade in this region was conducted by a group of Company's merchants. There were head merchants and under each head merchant there were several petty merchants. Fifty per cent of the merchants belonged to Chetty community and the rest were from Pillai, Rao, Reddy and Mudali castes. Unlike Madras there was no Brhamin merchant in the list of Cuddalore merchants.⁵

The Petty merchants procured cloth directly from the weavers. The trade was carried out according to the contract made with Company's merchants by the Agents of the East India Company. The terms and conditions regarding payment of advance, specification and duration for the procurement of cloth were very harsh. The contract made by John Davis, Chief, on behalf of the East India Company with Chinniahchetty in January 1685 exposed the severity and exploitation of the Company's merchants.⁶ Payment of advance partly in cash, partly in European goods, insisting the merchants to deliver the cotton textiles according to specification double the value of the advance received and settling the disputes between the Diwan and merchants by the merchants themselves ended in hardship and misery to the Indian merchants.

The English exported finest variety of cotton fabrics such as Salempores, moris, bethiles, percalla and romals. from ports of Devanampattinam and Cuddalore to South-east Asia. Hand

printed cotton fabrics produced in Cuddalore and Porto novo were exported to Manila in 1737.⁷ The Chintz, famous Coromandel production had a thriving market in the Persian Gulf, Burma, Siam, Malaya and Sumatra.⁸ Thus, at the exploitation of Indian weavers and Company merchants, English amazed wealth.

The strategic location of Cuddalore between Pondicherry and Porto novo, its connection with coastal towns such as Calcutta, Masulipattinam, Madras, Pulicat, Sadraspattinam, Pondicherry, Tranquebar, Karaikal, Nagore and Nagapattinam on the Coromandel coast, and Bombay, Surat, Goa, Diu, Tellicherry, Calicut, Travancore and Anjengo on the West coast enabled Cuddalore to grow into a port town .

Urban growth of Cuddalore

The weavers settlements were created in Cuddalore and the weavers in Porto novo and around Cuddalore were encouraged to settle in Cuddalore. In 1714, most of the waste lands within the bounds of Cuddalore was surveyed and plots were allotted to several sea-faring merchants from Portonovo. In order to avoid competition from the European merchants and for the timely procurement of cotton goods the Deputy Governor of Fort. St. David promised them security. Consequently, traders, weavers, dyers and painters came forward to settle down at Cuddalore in 1741.⁹ Tiruppapuliyur became centre of hand printing.¹⁰

In the early days of the English settlement the authority in several occasions started new suburbs; or Pettahs for the weavers on whose industry the profits of the Company so largely depended; attracting craftsmen from other districts either by making them conditional grants of land or by advancing them money for the building of houses and the purchase of looms. The people came to the place even from Salem and Kalahasti. One of the best known suburb is Brookespettah, near Vandipalayam founded by Mr. Henry Brooke, Chief of Cuddalore from 1767 to 1769. Other instances within the municipality are Lathomspet, named after Mr. Richard Loathom, Chief from 1773 to 1776. Cumingpet near Tiruppapuliyur was called after its founder Mr. William Cuming, Chief from 1778 to 1780. Kinchantpet between Tiruppapuliyur and Vandipalayam founded by the Richard Kinchant who was Commercial Resident at Cuddalore from 1798 onwards.¹¹

Urban face-lifts of Cuddalore Old Town

The Factory House, Residences of the Deputy Governor of Fort. St.David, Residential buildings of Commercial Resident, Chief of Cuddalore, Land and Sea Customs offices , barracks, residential area of the Europeans, Roman Catholic church, Christ Church under the control of the Society for the Propaganda of Christ Knowledge, the cemeteries in the Christ Church and the graveyards in the Sonagan street gave urban outlook. Besides, Charity school run by the East India Company, Barrack school and a school run by Society for the Propagation of the Gospel and teacher training school established by the Danish missionary, hospitals for the Indians and Europeans and the residences of officials, soldiers, invalid soldiers gave urban face-lift to Cuddalore. The colonial urban settlement was called White Town.

Industry

The industries connected with sea included fishing, rope making and boat building. “ Boat building is done at Porto novo and Cuddalore, more especially at the latter. In mud docks there, many of the masula boats which are used in Madras harbour are made. Nim (Neem tree- Azadirachta indica) and Vengai (Pterocarpus Marsupium) are the woods most used, and the natural angles of the timber are ingeniously utilised to construct knees and elbows for the frames of the boats without the weaker artificial joinings and splicings which would otherwise be necessary. Rope is generally made from coir by soaking and beating it in the usual way.”¹²

Social life of the Europeans

The Europeans celebrated ceremonies such as Baptism and festivals such as Christmas with great enthusiasm. On these occasions, palanquin bearers, peons and dancing girls were given presents as a reward for their services. The holding of feasts was for the Europeans a form of recreation. The feasts such as ‘Tiruppapuliur Feast’,¹³ ‘Peons sword’,¹⁴ and ‘Military and Gun-room Crew feast’¹⁵ revealed the military nature of the feasts and they were non-reciprocal.

The Portuguese married Indian women and settled in India. The Dutch married the women of Indo-Portuguese origin. They also had Indian women as concubines. The English soldiers at Cuddalore married Indian women especially, Popish Christians. After the end of the

Anglo-French wars, the barracks at Cuddalore were converted into residence of the invalid soldiers. The latter married Indian women and lived happily. The Europeans also married Eurasian women. However, unlike the Hindu and Muslim women on the west coast, their counterparts on the Coromandel coast were reluctant to marry the Europeans as the latter were beef and pork eaters, Hindu women married outside their caste lost their status in the society and due to the problem of conversion.¹⁶

The English soldiers who had left their families abroad indulged in prostitution. Drinking, riding and quarrelling with the natives were hobbies of the British soldiers.¹⁷ Gambling was one of the past-time among the high officials as well as priests. On the occasion of the feasts and festivals, the Europeans irrespective of sex drank and danced.

Disposal of the dead

The dead were buried in the graveyard and powerful among them were laid to rest in the cemeteries in church complex. The cemeteries located in the Sonagan street and Christ church complex are of historical importance and throws flood of light on the servants and their family members of the servants of English East India Company. The Sonagan street cemeteries are the oldest and these covers the graves of the wife and daughter of John Davis, Chief of Cuddalore from 1683 to 1687. Other graves here are those of Vicemus Grifith, third in the Fort. St. David council(1705); John Hallyburton, an honest brave man and sincere lover of his country murdered by a mutinous sepoy in Pondicherry in 1748 and wife of Charles Floyer, Governor of Fort St. David from 1747 to 1750.¹⁸

The cemetery and graveyard within the complex of the Christ church speak about famous Company's servants and military officers such as Hamilton Maxwell, the Colonel of the 74th Highlanders (1794); Colonel Sterling of the same regiment, commanding Pondicherry (1745), the wife of Colonel John Dupont, Commandant of Cuddalore (1801); the wife of Captain Harcourt Wood House commanding four Companies of the garrison (1777), John Rowley, senior judge of the provincial court of appeal (1805); Ernest William Fallow-field, Chief of Cuddalore from 1781 to 1785 and afterwards the member of the council of Fort. St. George(1816).¹⁹

Indian Society

The pre-colonial Hindu society, first three varnas excluding shudras was governed by Dharmashastras or norms relating to social obligations and ritual requirements. "... Jatis - hereditary groups arranged hierarchically, with unequal rights, a separation based on taboos of marriage rules, food and custom, and a resistance to unification with others"²⁰ continued in the names of Valangai and Idangai divisions excluding brahmanas and untouchables, without affecting the varna system till the dawn of the of the nineteenth century. Even though jati was different from varna or ritual status and viewed in terms of brahmanical culture, the English misunderstood these divisions as castes- Right hand caste and Left hand caste.

Right hand caste people engaged in agricultural occupation and artisans and traders belonged to the Left hand caste. Change of occupation was strictly prohibited. Violation of customary rules ended in disputes and some times murder. A small number of Jains, Buddhists, Muslims and Christians lived here. While inequality among Europeans was based on power and rank of a person, caste, occupation and wealth formed the basis of inequality in the Indian community. The pattern of houses, dress and food habits varied according to the castes. Inter-dining between various castes was prohibited. However, the wealthy chetties were considered inferior to the Right hand caste people.

Worship

Besides Siva and Vishnu, the Hindus particularly Sudras worshipped village deities or border deities like Ponniamman, Pidari, Draupathi, the favourite of the Pallis and the Ayyanar. The Sudra priests performed pujas in these temples.

Wedding and ritual

Wedding ceremonies and the rituals were religion oriented. Brahmin priests dominated in wedding, funeral and other domestic rituals of the Hindus. However, the wedding ceremony of the Maraikayars resembled that of the Hindus except employing the Brahmin priests. The Christians imitated the Europeans in wedding ceremonies and other rituals.

Belief in omens

The Hindus believed in omens. The cawing of a crow on a house indicated arrival of a guest. The appearance of tortoise in a house was inauspicious. It was supposed that the vulture or owl brought ill luck to the house on which it perches. Goat climbing the roof of a house foretold a disaster. It is a good omen to hear the bell ring, a cannon sound, the braying of an ass, the cry of a Brahmini kite or on first leaving the house, to catch sight of a married woman, a corpse, flowers, water or toddy pot. All classes believed that evil spirits were warded off by talisman (Raksha –bandhanam).²¹

Ideas on after life

The Hindus and Buddhists believed in incarnation. But Islam and Christianity rejected rebirth and incarnation of departed souls. Concept of rebirth in Hinduism, belief in hell and heaven were driving forces behind superstition. It was believed that a man who died holding the tail of the cow would live happily in future life.²² Tavernier observed that the Brahmin priests persuaded the women to commit sati so that they would go to other world where they could live happily along with their husbands. On the Coromandel coast women preferred to be interred along with their deceased husbands instead of being burnt alive .²³ Thus, superstition, ignorance and backwardness characterised the eighteenth century Hindu society.

Disposal of the dead

The Hindus cremated or buried the dead on the banks of the rivers, lakes and tanks. The Muslims and Christians buried the dead in the mosque complex and cemeteries respectively.

Social change.

The economic activities and administration of the English East India Company brought about changes in occupation, life style, food habits and way of thinking among Indians. The recognition of Right hand caste men as traders eroded the existing rigid caste divisions.²⁴ The first manifestation of Little tradition of westernization or the localised forms of western impacts were found in the commercial middle class in the eighteenth century. The members of this class

served as middlemen for the European traders. There were head merchants, petty merchants, clerks(gomasthas), interpreters(dobashes), cashiers(shroffs) and petty contractors(paikars) who travelled distant places for procuring cotton fabrics for the European trading companies. The rich among them began to use tables, chairs, spoons, forks and other articles used by the English officers purchased through auction.²⁵ There were changes among the educated Indians in food habits, hair style, dress and housing pattern. In short, they imitated European life-style.

The upper castes as well as the lower castes embraced Islam or Christianity either to escape from the cruel practice of sati or being ill treated and humiliated. Missionary activities and the educational service of the missionaries facilitated conversion of the Hindus into Christianity. While the indigenous system of education was favourable to the upper class only, the public schools opened by the missionaries and English East India Company enabled the people belonging to lower classes also to get the benefit of education.

Good roads improved the land transport in which bullock and horse-drawn carts were common. In water ways boats and ferries were used. Urban growth of Cuddalore led to emergence of cosmopolitan society which composed of Hindus, Buddhists, Jains, Muslims, Europeans, Anglo- Indians and Eurasians.

Conclusion

Though the urban area was distinct from the rural area in physical appearance due to the infrastructural facilities available in the former, the attitude of a section of the urban dwellers was still rural. In spite of western education superstitious practices still continued and could not be eradicated fully. “ that Indian cities, even some of the largest ones show sizable quarters which have preserved their rural character and in which life is carried on under general conditions only little different from those of the villages.”²⁶. Urbanization does not mean mere increase of concrete buildings of secular and religious nature. Likewise, mere increase of population alone cannot be criteria for assessing urban growth. The attitude, behaviour, culture, occupation and the life style of the people are also taken into account to measure the level of urbanization besides infrastructural facilities.

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